

Runoff Estimation in the Vrishabhavathi river basin using SCS Curve Number Model using Remote Sensing and GIS

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Abstract: The runoff in an area is generally affected by climatic factors such as precipitation type, its intensity and duration, distribution and direction of the prevailing storm along with other dominant climatic conditions. The major topographical factors affecting runoff are basin size, shape, elevation and arrangement of stream channels. The soil map shows different soil textures for which HSG is assigned with respect to the infiltration capacity. The soil and LU / LC maps are merged together using ArcGIS software. Then the CN II values are assigned based on the HSG and LU/LC classification unit. In modified SCS method we have to determine the CN II for ($I_a=0.05S$) values using the formula. Then CN I and CN III values are calculated using $CNII_{0.05}$ values. The daily runoff is computed on polygon wise for all the watersheds in the river basin. In view of these complex dependency factors, direct measurement of runoff is difficult or impossible. However, runoff can be estimated with the aid of hydrological models. In the study, Runoff is estimated by modified SCS-CN Model. This method is a proven efficient method for determining the accurate amount of runoff.

Key word: River Basin, Soil Map, LU/LC, SCS Curve Number.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantification of runoff is essential for efficient design, planning and management of urban river basin and river basin projects that deals with conservation and utilization of water for diverse purposes. The process of determination of surface runoff that take place in any drainage basin, understanding of complex rainfall and runoff process, which depends upon many geomorphologic and climatic factors are necessary. This has been done since long back by using conventional field observations and maps. However, it has been realized in the recent past, especially with the advent of the earth orbiting resource satellites that the input of remotely sensed data on basin parameters helps in improving the predictive capabilities of the runoff equations. Remote sensing has been extensively used as an important source of data and information for hydrologic modeling [01]. Bhaskar J. et.al; [02] has estimated runoff for urban catchment area with integration of RS and GIS based SCS CN method. Land use /land cover map shows the reduction of agricultural area between years 1976 to 2006. From the analysis it was observed that, water available from the heavy rainfall will produce more than three times what they required for the present-day population of the urban area. Hence it was suggested that, the conservation of the storm water through existing tanks and in new storage systems to solve the urban water problem. Abouzar Nasiri et.al; [03] attempted to study runoff curve number maps for captive catchment of Tehran by using GIS and remote sensing. It was based on factors such as vegetation, lands using, group of soil hydrology and hydrological conditions. Runoff curve numbers map was obtained by combining these maps in Arc GIS and SCS table. To evaluate the accuracy of the results, the maximum flow rate of flood which was obtained from curve numbers, was compared with the measured maximum flood rate at the watershed outlet and correctness of curve numbers were approved. Muhammad Ajmal et.al; [04] has estimated excess storm water i.e.; runoff using SCS CN model with GIS technique by changing the initial abstraction ratio values. Runoff was estimated from the three models for 15 watersheds in South Korea to assess the accurate runoff values. From this analysis, it was observed that initial abstraction ratio= 0.05 yielded accurate runoff. In the present research, USDA SCS CN [05] method has been adopted for quantification of runoff. The method is also called hydrologic soil cover complex number method. It is mainly based on the recharge capacity of a river basin. The recharge capacity can be determined by the antecedent moisture contents and by the physical characteristics of the river basin. The river basin has perennial water flow because of added sewage inflow. During heavy rainfall, the urban region faces problem due to flash flood. During flood the rainwater is mixed with sewage. This river basin is ungauged and falls under urban and rural region. Hence in the present study Vrishbhavathi river basin is divided into six watersheds to understand its behaviour with respect to rainfall. SCS-CN method is used in this study since the basin is ungauged.

II. STUDY AREA

The study area of this research is Vrishbhavathi River basin, which falls in Arkavathy catchment. This area lies between latitudes $12^{\circ} 44' 37''$ to $13^{\circ} 2' 31''$ N and longitudes $77^{\circ} 23' 14''$ to $77^{\circ} 34' 59''$ E. The catchment has an area of 360.28 sq. km. The mean annual rainfall of the River basin is 853.56 mm. Vrishabhavathi River is perennial due to the contribution of domestic and industrial effluents. The location of the study area is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1 Location map of the study area

III. MODIFIED SCS CURVE NUMBER MODEL AND INITIAL ABSTRACTION RATIO

The most important reason of SCS- CN model's wide applicability and acceptability lies in the fact that it accounts for most runoff producing watershed characteristics such as soil type, land use/treatment, surface condition and antecedent moisture condition. Fig.2 shows the methodology adopted for runoff estimation using SCS curve number method. In the year 1956, it was one of the most popular technique for computing the volume of surface runoff for a given rainfall event for agricultural, forest and urban watersheds. The method is very simple, easy to understand and applicable, stable, and handy for ungauged watersheds. Rainfall-runoff methods developed during the early 1940's utilized infiltration data for computing runoff amount. Andrews (1954) [6] developed a graphical rainfall-runoff method taking into account the soil texture, type and amount of cover, and conservation practices, combined into what is referred to as soil-cover complex or soil-vegetation-land-use (SVL) complex (Miller and Cronshey, 1989) [7]. Stube and Johnson, 1990[8] and Ponce and Hawkins, 1996[9] critically examined this method, clarified its conceptual and empirical basis, delineated its capabilities, limitation and uses. The fairly precise value of initial abstraction $I_a = 0.2S$ was found through many studies of smaller agricultural watersheds, but it was thought to be very conservative by some scientists. So, researchers have used these factors as well as mathematical transformations to modify and improve the SCS-CN method. The initial abstraction ratio (I_a/S) plays most important role in the calculated runoff depth, the hydrograph peak and the time distribution of runoff. Woodward et al. (2003) [10] found that an initial abstraction ratio of $\lambda = 0.05$ as the best fit value for 252 out of 307 (approximately five out six) watersheds, as this value produced a higher coefficient of determination (R^2) and a lower standard error (SE) than other values.

Fig..2 Modified SCS CN model flow chart to estimate surface runoff

During the year 2003 to 2012 a systematic study has been carried out by group of researchers and professionals “(Woodward et.al[10]; Mishra et.al[11]; Soulis et.al[12]; Hawkins et al[13]; Baltas et al[14])” found that a value of $I_a = 0.05S$ fits rainfall-runoff conditions much better than $I_a = 0.2S$. Since our river basin is spread over urban and semi-rural area there will be chance of higher runoff and low infiltration. The recent studies have carried out in India by Nayak T.R[15] for Narmada River basin and observed good results from this modified SCS CN model. Hence an attempt has been made to estimate surface runoff by considering the $I_a = 0.05S$ for the Vrishbhavathi river basin.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Water balance equation is the baseline data for the SCS curve number model. Fig 3 and 4 shows the relationship between rainfall, runoff and surface retention and representation of mass curve for SCS method was developed by McCuen, 1982; [16] in the year 1982. Procedure for quantification of runoff by modified SCS CN method is given in the flow chart shown in Fig .5

Fig 3

Fig 4

Fig 3 and. 4 shows the relationship between rainfall, runoff and surface retention and representation of mass curve for SCS method was developed by McCuen, 1982

Fig .5 Quantification of runoff by modified SCS CN method

V. DETERMINATION OF CURVE NUMBER (CN)

The CN values were determined from HSG and antecedent moisture conditions of the river basin. Table 1 shows the curve number (AMC-II) obtained from the literature to assign curve number for the present land use classification. The CN values were assigned polygon wise for each land use /land cover units based on the HSG prepared by soil map. After obtaining weighted CN for AMC-II condition ($I_a=0.2S$), generate $CN_{0.05}$ for the condition ($I_a=0.05S$) using empirical equation given in the flow chart (Fig.5). Fig 6 shows the Landuse/land cover map of the Study area. Fig 7 Shows the Soil Map of the Study area.

Table 1 Runoff curve numbers for (AMC II) hydrologic soil cover complex

Sl No	Land use/land cover classification	Hydrologic soil group			
		A	B	C	D
1	Agricultural land without conservation (Kharif)	72	81	88	91
2	Kharif + rabi (double crop)	62	71	88	91
3	Agriculture plantation	45	53	67	72
4	Land with scrub	36	60	73	79
5	Barren rocky / stony waste / sheet rock area	45	66	77	83
6	Degraded forest	45	66	77	83
7	Forest plantation	25	55	70	77
8	Dense Grass land / Grazing land	39	61	74	80
9	Town / Cities /Roadway	57	72	81	86
10	Industrial area	81	88	91	93
11	River/Stream	97	97	97	97
12	Fallow land	76	85	90	93
13	Lake / Tanks	100	100	100	100
14	Tree groves	39	61	74	80
15	Village	59	74	82	86
16	Waterlogged area	100	100	100	100
17	Moist & dry deciduous open forest	36	60	73	79
18	Mixed vegetation	74	83	88	90
19	Mining / Industrial wasteland/Railway line	77	86	91	94
20	Land without scrub	48	67	77	83
21	Gullied / Revinous land	72	82	87	89
22	Scrub forest	55	72	81	86

(Source: Ven Te Chow, 1981)[16]

VI. HYDROLOGIC SOIL GROUP (HSG)

The hydrological soil groups as defined by the Soil Conservation Service (1972) were categorized into A, B, C and D based on infiltration rate. By analyzing the soil texture, estimate the minimum infiltration rates, to classify the HSG using the values shown in Table 2. The hydrological soil group map is used to get curve numbers from Table 1.

Group A: Soils in this group have a low runoff potential (high-infiltration rates) even when thoroughly wetted. They consist of deep, well to excessively well-drained sands or gravels. These soils have a high rate of water transmission.

Group B: Soils in this group have moderate infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consists chiefly of moderately deep to deep, well-drained to moderately well-drained soils with moderately fine to moderately coarse textures. These soils have a moderate rate of water transmission.

Group C: Soils have slow infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consist chiefly of soils with a layer that impedes the downward movement of water, or soils with moderately fine-to fine texture. These soils have a slow rate of water transmission.

Group D: Soils have a high runoff potential (very slow infiltration rates) when thoroughly wetted. These soils consist chiefly of clay soils with high swelling potential, soils with a permanent high-water table, soils with a clay layer near the surface, and shallow soils over nearly impervious material. These soils have a very slow rate of water transmission. Fig 8 shows Hydrological Soil Group map of the Study area.

Table 2 HSG classification based on infiltration rate

Soil Group	Range of infiltration rate (mm/hr)
A	7.62-11.43
B	3.81-7.62
C	1.27-3.81
D	0-1.27

VII. ANTECEDENT MOISTURE CONDITIONS (AMCS)

Antecedent moisture condition (AMC) refers to water content of soil surface which is obtained by total rainfall of 5 days period preceding storm. The AMC value is intended to reflect the effect of infiltration on both the volume and rate of runoff according to the infiltration curve. Runoff potential increases with increase of wetness index of the soil surface. The SCS developed three antecedent soil-moisture conditions and labeled them as I, II, III. These AMC's correspond to the following soil conditions. Table 3 shows the AMC's classification.

AMC I: Soils are dry but not to the wilting point; satisfactory cultivation has taken place.

AMC II: Average conditions.

AMC III: Heavy rainfall or light rainfall and low temperatures have occurred within last 5 days; Saturated soils. Table 3 shows the seasonal rainfall units for the AMC classification and for CN.

Table 3 Antecedent moisture conditions (AMCs)

AMC CLASS	Five days antecedent rainfall (mm)	
	Dormant season	Growing season
I	< 12.7 mm	<35.56 mm
II	12.7-27.94 mm	35.56-53.34 mm
III	> 27.94 mm	>53.34 mm

The curve numbers for AMC II condition were taken by overlaying the land use/land cover and hydrological soil groups of the Vrishbhavathi river basin. From AMC II condition the curve numbers for AMC I and III were obtained from the following general empirical equations:

$$CN_I = \frac{4.2 \times CN_{II}}{10 - (0.058 \times CN_{II})}$$

$$CN_{III} = \frac{23 \times CN_{II}}{10 + (0.13 \times CN_{II})}$$

Table 4 shows the weighted curve numbers estimated for watersheds within the river basin. All the three AMC conditions were considered for the estimation of runoff from the watersheds of Vrishbhavathi river basin. Fig 9 shows the modified curve number map for AMC II of the study area ($I_a = 0.05S$). The quantity of runoff estimated from each watershed is tabulated in Table 5.

Based on mean annual runoff obtained, runoff potential for watersheds has been classified and is shown in Table 5. Fig 10 shows runoff depth map of the Vrishbhavathi river basin. [17]

Fig 6 Land use/ land cover map

Fig 7 Soil Map

Fig 8 Hydrological Soil Group Map

Fig 9 Modified Curve Number Map Map

Table 4 Weighted curve numbers for watersheds

Watershed No	Area (km ²)	CN II	CNII _{0.05}	CN I	CNI _{0.05}	CN III	CNIII _{0.05}
1	80.73	85	79	71	63	92	89
2	62.08	79	71	63	54	89	83
3	75.73	72	63	55	45	84	77
4	44.02	72	63	56	46	84	77
5	35.27	66	55	48	38	80	71
6	62.46	74	66	59	50	85	79

Table 5 Classification of runoff potential for the study area

Watershed no	Area (km ²)	Mean runoff depth (mm)	Classification of runoff potential	Scale of measurement
W 1	80.73	183.99	Very high	>160
W 2	62.08	144.04	High	140-160
W 3	75.73	103.96	Medium	100-120
W 4	44.02	104.28	Medium	100-120
W 5	35.27	77.78	Low	<100
W 6	62.46	129.77	Moderate	120-140

Fig 10 Runoff Depth Map of the Vrishabhavathi River Basin

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The river basin is characterized by medium rainfall, with irregular and erratic rainfall pattern. The perennial source of water is available for the river basin due to sewage flow. Surface runoff is the important parameter in the water balance equation is necessary for the efficient planning and management of the available water. The SCS curve number method uses, minimum data as input, and gives reliable output, using the remote sensing and GIS techniques in most efficient way. Minimum runoff was recorded in the watershed-5 with 77.78 mm and maximum runoff in the watershed-1 with 183.99mm. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the performance of the procedure using land cover database from remotely sensed data. The study also serves as an input for the management of the river basin with available water resources.

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